

THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE PIPES: AN OVERVIEW OF ADVANCED FULL SCALE TESTING APPROACHES

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AXIAL FATIGUE WITH DIC

Use of digital image correlation (DIC) on full scale fatigue tests allows strain details to be captured throughout the fatigue life of a pipe. This level of detail enables complex models to be developed, facilitating a deeper understanding of composite fatigue life beyond simple S-N curves and to better predict the long-term service life of a pipe.

BEND TESTING: FULL SCALE 4-POINT BEND FATIGUE TESTING

Composite pipes experience bending from manufacturing, storage, deployment and in-service. The full scale 4-point bend rig allows tests to replicate the various bending strains experienced by the pipe at different phases in the pipe's lifecycle.

Real World Bending Conditions

Bending Conditions Replicated at Full Scale

BURST TESTING: OPEN END, CLOSED END, AND BEND AND BURST

The strength of the pipe is affected by the ratio of axial and hoop stresses. To validate predictive models, several tests are conducted which can vary the ratio of axial and hoop stresses when the pipe is internally pressurised. This can be varied from a mixed mode load case (closed end burst and bend and burst tests) through to a purely hoop driven load case (open end burst).

Closed End Burst Test

Open End Burst

Bend and Burst Fixture

